

Boron Acylates

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A detailed study of the reactions of methyl and ethyl borates with acetic and propionic anhydrides has been carried out. Formation of a tetra-acylate product $B_2O(OAc)_4$ under all conditions confirms the results of Gerrard and co-workers⁹. Formation of the oxygen-bridge product has been confirmed by its reactions with hexylene glycol and pinacol.

Pictet and Glezenoff¹ first prepared boron acetate by the interaction of boric oxide or acid and acetic anhydride and assigned to it the structure $(CH_3COO)_3B$. They used it as a starting material for the synthesis of a wide range of tri-alkyl and tri-aryl borates. Dimroth², however, repeated the preparation of boron acetate from boric anhydride and found the ratio of acetic acid: boric acid as 2:1. In view of this, he concluded that the product was tetra-acyl pyroborate and not tri-acyl borate:

The work of Dimroth² was, however, ignored by later workers³⁻⁸ as all of them considered 'boron acetate' to possess the tri-acyl structure. Gerrard and Wheelans⁹ by carrying out reactions between boric acid and acetic anhydride in a number of ratios found in each case the ratio (determined by a special method of Morgan and Tunstall¹⁰) as 2:1 and not 3:1. According to Ahmad and Khundkar⁴, the reaction between boric acid and acetic anhydride yielded boron tri-acetate. Hayter *et al.*¹¹ confirmed the pyroborate structure for boron acetate by determination of molecular weight analysis, and X-ray diffraction.

In view of the successful preparation of aluminium tri-acetate¹², it was considered of interest to study the reactions of alkyl orthoborates with acetic anhydride in different

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molar ratios (1:3, 1:2, and 1:1), whereby a white crystalline product was obtained which on analysis was found to be tetra-acetyl pyroborate. The yields of the pyroborate and the unchanged reactants indicate that the reaction takes place in the following stoichiometric ratio:

The reaction, however, must be occurring stepwise. As none of the intermediate products (ethyl acetyl borates) could be isolated, it appeared that these were unstable at the refluxing temperature employed for the reactions. The reaction mixtures of ethyl borate and acetic anhydride in different molar ratios were therefore left for several hours at room temperature. In these cases also, the only product, which crystallised out, was the pyroborate. The reaction was, however, slow and on removing the crystals of pyroborate, a fresh crop was gradually obtained.

The reactions (at room temperature as well as under refluxing conditions) between methyl borate and acetic anhydride, also in different molar ratios, led to the formation of the tetra-acetyl pyroborate. Boron tri-acetate or the mixed alkoxide boron acetate could not be obtained in these cases also.

Besides the analysis of boron and acetate, the identity of tetra-acetyl pyroborate has been further confirmed by its reactions with 2-methylpentane-2,4-diol¹³ and pinacol¹⁴. The reaction in 1:2 molar ratio afforded bis-(1,1,3-trimethyltrimethylene)pyroborate and bis-(tetramethylethylene)pyroborate respectively. On heating with excess of 2-methylpentane-2,4-diol, 1,1,3-trimethyltrimethylene-bis-(1,1,3-trimethyltrimethylene borate) was obtained as a colorless viscous liquid.

EXPERIMENTAL

All-glass apparatus with standard interchangeable joints was used and special precautions were taken to exclude moisture. Ethyl borate was prepared by the action of boron trichloride on ethanol in CCl_4 . The reactants were mixed slowly in a bath of freezing mixture and the mixture was refluxed for a considerable time for removing the liberated HCl. Finally, the ethyl borate was fractionated through a long column at 118° and the alkoxide analysed. [Found: B, 7.36; OEt, 92.60. Calc. for $\text{B}(\text{OEt})_3$: B, 7.36; OEt, 92.64%].

For the estimation of boron, a known amount of the compound was dissolved in water and mannitol (~2.0 g.) was added. The complex formed was titrated against a standard NaOH solution.

When both borate and acetate groups were attached in a compound, a known weight of the compound was titrated against the standard NaOH solution, using bromothymol blue as an indicator. The acetate groups were first titrated and a sharp end point was observed. Then mannitol was added and the solution was retitrated with the same NaOH solution. The first volume of NaOH was used by acetate groups and the second volume was consumed by the borate complex.

13. Mehrotra and Srivastava, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1962, 1032.

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Reaction of Ethyl Borate with Acetic Anhydride in Molar Ratio of 1:3 (with Refluxing).
 —Ethyl borate (6.70 g., 1M) was mixed with acetic anhydride (13.90 g., 3M). No appreciable heat was evolved. The mixture was refluxed for 3 hrs. in a bath at 110°. A white solid crystallised from the reaction mixture. The mother liquor was decanted and the product was washed with benzene and dried at 22°/0.2 mm; yield 95%. {Found: B, 7.81; acetate, 85.40. Calc. for [(AcO)₂B]₂O: B, 7.90; acetate, 86.2%}.

TABLE I

Reactions of alkyl borates (ethyl and methyl) with acetic anhydride in different molar ratios (without refluxing).

Molar ratio. alkyl borate: Ac ₂ O.	Duration of ageing.	*Yield%.	% Boron.		% Acetyl.	
			Found.	Calc.	Found.	Calc.
Ethyl borate.						
1 : 1	50 hrs.	80	7.87	7.90	85.30	86.24
1 : 2	48	75	7.90	7.90	85.80	86.24
1 : 3	48	86	8.00	7.90	85.60	86.24
Methyl borate.						
1 : 1	36	80	8.00	7.90	86.20	86.24
1 : 2	36	84	7.89	7.90	86.50	86.24
1 : 3	40	86	7.89	7.90	86.30	86.24
1 : 1 (with refluxing)	..	90	7.88	7.90	86.00	86.24

*On the basis of acetic anhydride.

Reaction of Ethyl Borate with Propionic Anhydride in Molar Ratio of 1:3.—A mixture of ethyl borate (4.14 g., 1M) and propionic anhydride (11.40 g., 3M) was refluxed for about 3 hrs. in a bath at 120°. A white product separated which was washed with benzene, dried at 20°/0.2 mm and analysed. {Found: B, 6.61; propionate, 87.54. Calc. for [(Propionate)₂B]₂O: B, 6.56; propionate, 88.59%}.

Reaction of Tetra-acetyl Pyroborate with 2-Methylpentane-2,4-diol (Hexylene Glycol) in Molar Ratio of 1:2.—Hexylene glycol (1.76 g., 2M) was mixed with tetra-acetyl pyroborate (2.06 g., 1M) and the reaction mixture was thoroughly shaken. Heat was evolved and the liberated acetic acid was removed under reduced pressure at 30°/0.2mm. The remaining liquid on distillation provided a colorless liquid which was analysed. Yield of distilled dihexylene pyroborate was 90% of the theoretical. [Found: B, 7.9. Calc. for (C₆H₁₂O₄B)₂O: B, 8.0%].

The above compound on exposure to atmospheric moisture was found to be hydrolysed to hexylene hydrogen borate, a crystalline solid. (Found: B, 7.50. Calc. for C₆H₁₂O₄.BOH: B, 7.52%).

Reaction of Tetra-acetyl Pyroborate with Hexylene Glycol in Molar Ratio of 1:>3.—Considerable heat was evolved on mixing hexylene glycol (7.01 g., 4.3M) and tetra-acetyl

pyroborate (3.80 g., 1 *M*) with liberation of free acetic acid. The acetic acid was removed at 30°/0.1 mm and excess glycol distilled at 120°/0.1 mm. The product (dihexylene hexylene di-borate) was finally distilled at 128°/0.1 mm and analysed. [Found: B, 5.7. Calc. for (C₆H₁₄O₂)₃B₂O: B, 5.8%].

Reaction of Tetra-acetyl Pyroborate with Pinacol in Molar Ratio of 1:2.—Tetra-acetyl pyroborate (10.50 g., 1 *M*) and pinacol (9.06 g., 2 *M*) were mixed together and the reaction mixture was refluxed for an hour in a bath at 130° with benzene. The volatile fractions were distilled under reduced pressure. A white product (m.p. 56-58°) distilled at 115°/0.1 mm, which was analysed. (Found: B, 8.00. Calc. for C₁₂H₂₄B₂O₅: B, 8.01%).

DISCUSSION

The reactions of alkoxides of titanium^{15,16,18}, aluminium¹², and zirconium¹⁷ with acid anhydrides have been studied in detail in these laboratories. Although there is a clear parallelism and interesting relationship between the acylate derivatives of the four elements, the boron derivatives differ from the rest in the instability of all the possible mixed alkoxide acylates which could not be isolated even under mild conditions. This is in conformity with the properties of mixed alkoxides of boron which are very unstable and have been found to disproportionate¹⁹ most readily into symmetrical orthoborates. The mixed alkoxides of aluminium are stable, distillable products²⁰. Their stability is probably due to the π -bond in the bridge structures formed intermolecularly. Boron, on the other hand, tries to attain the octet configuration by back co-ordination and formation of the π -bonds within the molecule itself.

Thus due to instability of the mixed alkoxide acylates of boron, the reaction between alkyl borates and acid anhydrides results in the formation of the pyroborate only, irrespective of the molar ratios of the reactants. The only product, which crystallises, is the tetra-acetyl pyroborate, as it appears to be the most stable as well as the least soluble. Attempt was made to vary this effect (if possible) by taking propionic anhydride instead of acetic anhydride, but the reaction between ethyl borate and propionic anhydride in the molar ratio of 1:3 was also found to yield only the tetra-propionyl pyroborate. The above mechanism, although similar to those suggested in the cases of similar reactions with titanium and zirconium alkoxides are, however, highly speculative as it has not been possible, in spite of repeated efforts, to isolate any of the intermediate products.

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